

Deliverable D3.4

Updated infrastructure status report and updated roadmap

Project Title Grant agreement no	Genomic Data Infrastructure Grant agreement 101081813		
Project Acronym (EC Call)	GDI		
WP No & Title	WP3: Deployment of 1+MG National Nodes		
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Contractual delivery date	31/10/2025	Actual delivery date	19/12/2025
Delayed	Yes		
Partner(s) contributing to deliverable	UU		
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Acknowledgements			
Reviewers	Rob Hooft, HRI; Dylan Spalding, CSC		

Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
06/11/2025	vo.1	Anna Hagwall, UU	First draft initiated
17/11/2025	vo.2	Anna Hagwall, UU	Draft ready for review

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

25/11/2025	v0.3	Anna Hagwall, UU	Updated after review
02/12/2025	v0.4	Ellie Younger, ELIXIR Hub	Sent for MB review
19/12/2025	v1.0	Ellie Younger, ELIXIR Hub	Submitted

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1. Executive Summary

Since deliverable 3.3 about 1.5 years ago, the governance model anticipated by the project has been adjusted, replacing the centralized model with an EDIC that is responsible for the data access decision with a decentralized model with an coordinating EDIC that advises on the data access decision to be taken by the data controllers in the member countries, under responsibility of the national data holders, and based on dynamic consent and national laws and regulations. This change in legal basis requires technical changes: rather than facilitating decisions from a central body we will now need to support National Contact Points and the datasets' data controllers. Additionally, WP3 and WP5 have identified that some parts of the previously expected Minimal Viable Product (MVP) cannot be achieved until the EDIC is in place, which cannot be assumed to happen before the end of the GDI project, due to the administrative process to create an EDIC.

To support the new scenario, the technical end goal for GDI has been reframed. Of high importance is that the requirements for demonstrating that a node is technically ready for production have been reduced; countries can voluntarily contribute more by demonstrating further features. However, the requirements on interoperability, security, etc will remain and the focus on shaping security procedures will increase the coming months.

This deliverable provides an overview of the changes affecting WP3 and how WP3 has adjusted.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi-party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers</p>	No

(e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Methods

The work in deliverable 3.4 relies heavily on the planning and execution made by Pillar II leads, WP3 leads, WP5 leads, vanguard nodes, and product development teams. Most of the planning has been done during WP3 meetings or dedicated meetings, mostly online and sometimes in person, making use of the GDI Google drive tools and Miro.

Additionally, input from other Pillar II members at various meetings and workshops has been essential. The Pillar II technical workshop in Paris this year on 15 - 17 October was essential to the plans forming, and a reason for the pre-announced delay of this deliverable by a month.

To define the February Feature Freeze (FFF) - a term referring to the definition of the end goal of the project and the set of technical work needed to reach it - there were also meetings including members from Pillars I and III.

For understanding the ambitions and challenges related to the countries, we have acquired reports from all countries aiming for operation at the end of the GDI project.

4. Description of work accomplished

This chapter is structured in a chronological order, giving an overview of the progression of the infrastructure.

4.1 Milestone 8: The basis for the technical end goal

Six countries (ES, FI, LUX, NO, PT, SE) participated in completing milestone 8. Examples of the efforts (4.1.1. and 4.1.2. below) were also demonstrated in video recordings¹. In autumn 2024, this was expected to be what all countries aiming for operation must be able to do, with real data in 2026, in order to reach production state.

However, that ambition has changed, as explained below.

4.1.1 Beacon search, access application, and analysis of cancer datasets in SPE

This use case is built on MS7, and has a customised synthetic dataset used for a relevant use case - colorectal cancer. A user logged on to the GDI portal could search for phenotypic data among individuals in the GDI infrastructure via the Beacon interface, receive a result list of applicable datasets, apply for access to the datasets using REMS within the GDI User Portal by providing relevant documentation such as ethical permits, and then be granted access, have data transferred to a secure processing environment and analyse it using relevant software (cBioPortal).

¹ The two oldest videos here:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLweO8RYcVPDM2s4vQGfmJ7PRdVqYVqW1J>

4.1.2 Allele frequency search on single nucleotide variation related to Covid-19

This use case was added during the Pillar II technical workshop in September 2024, during the cross-pillar meeting. It would add a means to view interesting statistical data (allele frequency data) without even needing to log on, as the data was aggregated and therefore not considered personal data. This use case is within infectious diseases, which also had not been demonstrated earlier. The methodology would, however, also be useful for e.g. rare diseases.

As above, a Beacon query was used. However, this time, a new separate interface was used, searching for pre-calculated allele-frequency statistics. Using this interface and the synthetic data, it was shown that it is possible to single out genetic variants that make a person susceptible to severe Covid-19.

4.2 FFF - February Feature Freeze

In years 2 and 3 of the project, there have been discussions on what the Minimal Viable Product (MVP) is that the GDI project should deliver to the 1+MG initiative at the end. About a year ago, we made an effort to define the end goal for the GDI project timeframe (as opposed to the end goal of 1+MG or anything in between). This end goal would be known as the February Feature Freeze (FFF). This name indicated the need of the system developers in the project to be working towards a scope agreed between all pillars, without the risk of continued “feature creep” that can hamper progress in complex technical projects.

After a few dedicated online workshops on the data governance's effect on the infrastructure, led by the WP6 lead, a large group of GDI members participated in a workshop² to identify possible gaps in the infrastructure in relation to the user journeys described by Pillar III,³ other data governance aspects⁴, and data submission⁵.

The list of gaps was processed further by product owners and Pillar II leads (which constitute the WP5 leads and WP3 leads). An in-person workshop resulted in a plan for April 2026 called the FFF, February Feature Freeze, handled by Pillar II. Additionally, we planned for an additional demo with synthetic data in Oct 2026 called the FFF demo, handled by Pillar III. The work required to reach FFF was added to a Pillar II planning board in GitHub⁶ with deadlines. Several work items on a board made up “virtual” (non-official) quarterly milestones.

The progress was monitored monthly by WP3.

² https://docs.google.com/document/d/1lnR_bBatmM5XMc87_oNEOADywbOapRQBh314uvE7aws/edit?usp=sharing (internal doc)

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/17661188>

⁴ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TiLYVeaJJRHyyDggeoThCrSr3aOXFyfrz9NZQKvoG2s/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.749qkw454cv> (internal doc)

⁵ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HaL4rodnrngnylqIEDmcN3RhG3RlnsHTMxbHZyY9oGio/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.isjwlko4hoxs> (internal doc)

⁶ <https://github.com/orgs/GenomicDataInfrastructure/projects/6/views/1> (Private account)

4.3 Decentralized controllership

Soon after the definition of the FFF, in May 2025, there was a member state vote in favour of having a decentralised controllership for the data access decision as an interim governance until sharing genomics through EHDS is established. The decentralised controllership transfers power (data controllership) from the central EDIC to the data providers and, with (likely in most countries) consent as a legal basis for sharing, puts more workload on the countries. This is described elsewhere, and the choice was made based on thorough investigations by the 1+MG ELSI working group and GDI Pillar I.

This meant that we probably would need to adjust the FFF. We assessed the situation the following months to reach a conclusion.

One conclusion was that we would focus on the Genome of Europe (GoE) data to demonstrate operation in GDI, as the GoE project would be able to provide real data to real users and has its own legal basis for primary use. GoE has its own use cases, and to execute these no data re-use and no consent is necessary). This was agreed at the management board meeting in July.

4.4 Node alignment

In August 2025, the countries were informed about plans and some alternative ways were suggested for the technical deployment. The proposal was to focus on allele frequency search and align it with the corresponding use case in the GoE project. Next to the strictly quality-vetted genomic data, GoE collects only the phenotypic data for age, sex at birth, and country of birth, so there can be pre-calculated cohorts for these three factors in each participating country. The focus on the primary use in the GoE project avoids heavy administrative work load due to distributed data controllership, based on the current interpretation of our GDPR obligations in Pillar I.

The alternative scenarios concerned how to technically handle the access management, now that the central EDIC office no longer would make a decision on access requests:

1. Centrally: with a central REMS
2. Partly decentralised: with a central REMS and a local access application tool (such as REMS)
3. Decentralised: with a local access application tool only

All countries were requested to respond to a questionnaire, and present their views at an online workshop on node alignment arranged by WP5 leads, supported by WP3 leads. 16 countries responded and 13 presented.

This workshop gave valuable insights into the plans for the countries, such as that 14 found it likely to join the EDIC during the GDI timeline, 15 know who will operate the infrastructure in production, 11 know who will be the National Contact Point (NCP) in their country, and 5 will use a structure based upon FEAGA (Federated European Genome-phenome Archive). Finally, 8 state that it is planned for

and feasible to use GoE data in GDI during the GDI time frame. All responding countries supported aiming for aggregated allele frequencies.

The decentralised technical option for access request management was omitted as it would not align with the governance requirement on a harmonised interface for the users and also for the central EDIC office that would make recommendations for 1+MG compliant data (for EDIC-connected countries only).

All countries found scenario 1 or 2 for the access management acceptable or preferred. The final decision of the implementation per country was not expected at this point in time.

4.5 Four steps towards deployment

During the spring of 2025, Pillar II leads (WP3 and WP5 leads) identified four actions that would assist GDI countries to reach deployment and operation.

1. Each country sets up a local national test environment
2. Pillar II sets up a central test environment for the countries to use
3. Product owners create an About page in GitHub with information about the GDI infrastructure
4. Countries were coupled in the GDI buddies programme: countries aiming for operational that were not vanguard and have no Product Ownership assist countries aiming for deployment with their setup.

4.5.1 Local national test environment

Each country sets up a local test environment and registers the URL to their local Beacon and FDP instance in a central register. All registered national services are now monitored using Uptime Kuma by WP4, who also can assist with troubleshooting. Uptime Kuma is an open-source, free, and self-hosted real-time monitoring tool that continuously monitors if an IP address or website is live⁷.

The deadline for countries aiming for operation to register their Beacon and FDP services was 1 September 2025. The countries that had provided their information 1.5 week later were these:

FDP: Estonia, Finland, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

Beacon: Estonia, Finland, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

Most other partners are expected to register the URLs of their test services over the coming months. We will also monitor the production instances from each country later in the project.

4.5.2 Central test environment for the countries to use

The central test environment was established as a "sandbox". Developers in the project can submit dummy data to this, to test the infrastructure and processes. Meanwhile, the regular instances of the

⁷ <https://uptimekuma.org/#screenshots>

central products remain intact and can be used for demonstration purposes to national stakeholders etc.

4.5.3. About page in GitHub

The About page is published with descriptions of the starter kit and links to the planning board for the products. In the coming weeks and months, there will be information and instructions added regarding deployment, data upload and more.

4.5.4 GDI buddies

Countries aiming for operation who have not been vanguard nodes nor had product ownership will contribute to the common good of the project by assisting countries aiming for deployment. Groups of buddy countries have been formed and the first meetings are taking place during November 2025.

4.6 Task forces

GDI partners and users need to rely on that the infrastructure is secure and of high quality and is suitable for the datasets of interest. Task forces have been established to cater for the inter-product needs.⁸

One example is the metadata task force which informs the infrastructure developers which metadata to expect and the data providers which data to include. This includes ELSI metadata. Another is the productionisation task force which provides recommendations on what is needed for a product to be production-ready and also some important aspects for a node to be operational.. The API task force provides flexibility for the countries that wish to use other products than those provided in the starter kit.

4.7 FitSM

As part of WP4, FitSM⁹ has been decided as the recommended IT service management system for GDI. The planning for implementation is currently underway and will clarify the expectations on the countries and central services regarding service availability, security measures and more. It is important to note that it is not sufficient to deploy products and connect them with the central products to become truly operational.

4.8 New direction

At the Pillar II technical workshop in Paris 15 - 17 October 2025, it became clear what technical goals we can aim for. The terminology and scope is changing as illustrated below.

The name FFF, considered project slang, has been abandoned. Instead, the new roadmap refers to the MAP, which stands for Maximum Achievable Product. and the goal has been divided into one

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17580537> D5.3. section 4.1.8

⁹ <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

required step and three optional steps. During November 2025, the project board in GitHub is refined and updated to correspond to the new goals.

Goals

MAP stage 1 is what all countries must achieve with real data to reach production state. This includes the Allele Frequency Beacon which contains aggregated non-personal data provided by GoE as well as searches based on metadata in FDP.

MAP stage 2 is what some countries can achieve with real data. This includes progressing from search results in the User Portal, by linking to external application access processes connected to storage and secure processing environments. This will be performed with data governed by GoE to be used by the GoE consortium, so called primary use.

Individual search PoC is a Beacon search by a logged on user, similar to the first part of the cancer use case part of Milestone 8, described above. Here, it would be on synthetic data, as the EDIC will not be in place on time, but making use of the GDI processes. For countries that have a suitable SPE available, the PoC will continue from the search to applying for data access and analysing it (dotted arrows).

*Note: **Federated analysis PoC** is the new name of FFF demo. This is handled by Pillar III and described elsewhere.*

The workflow is illustrated below:

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GDI From data discovery to analysis in 2026

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A more technical view on the products and components needed is provided below:

The progress on product development (and SOP creation) in the GitHub board is monitored bi-weekly by WP3.

4.9 National goals

The next step is that all countries aiming for production state must determine if they will deploy a centralized or partly decentralised technical access management model and which goal they will strive for: MAP stage 1 will be mandatory for operation, while stage 2, individual search PoC and federated analysis PoC are all optional.

A questionnaire will be sent out shortly, and the progress of the countries will be monitored in WP3.

5. Results

The roadmap for the infrastructure has gone through several phases, as described above:

- been set in the FFF
- been monitored
- become partly obsolete due to external factors
- been restructured
- is now reaching a final state and is monitored more often.

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Regarding the national deployment:

- In October 2024, vanguard nodes who participated in milestone 8 demonstrated an entire use case tailored process with synthetic data.
- In September 2025, countries self-reported status updates on the technical deployment at the node alignment workshop.
- From autumn 2025, countries with deployed test beacons and test FDPs are monitored.
- The roadmap for national deployment is being created in November 2025.
- The progress on national deployment will be monitored at the WP3 meetings starting November 2025.
- All countries report overall progress in the quarterly reports to the GDI coordinators.

6. Discussion

In the 1.5 years since the last update, the roadmap has undergone significant changes.

These changes are primarily due to

1. changes in the governance model
2. based on new insights
3. ideas on how to tackle challenges in different countries, taking into account their specific needs and limitations.

We aim for interoperability, security, a minimum level of features, and cater for national preferences.

7. Next steps

These are the main next steps:

1. Identify which countries will aim for which goals
2. Monitor progress of countries
3. Monitor product enhancements
4. Arrange another technical workshop, this time focused on production
5. Deadline for goals

The countries will determine if they can make the mandatory goal (MAP stage 1), and also if they wish to participate in the optional goals. A factor to consider is the GDI partners' relationship to the national GoE partner, and if there is data available. The Readme in GitHub, the central test environment, and a progress board will provide the necessary assistance for them in their endeavour.

The countries' progress will be tracked during the WP3 meetings in the coming months. The production-ready environments will also be monitored with Uptime Kuma, as the test environments.

The product enhancements will also be tracked, at dedicated meetings.

In the spring 2026, we will arrange an additional Pillar II technical workshop with an emphasis on reaching production. This was not part of the initial project plan, but is added as the need was identified. Soon after, there is a deadline for production-readiness with real GoE data for primary use, leaving 6 months for further improvements, as well as MAP stage 2 and the two PoCs until, in a year from now, the project ends.

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